

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NDEKSIA SOUMAI****FIRST NAME: ESTHER****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401 D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. See the sentences below and mark the right answer for plagiarism.

- Plagiarism is when the writer does not give credit to a source of information, only when this information is presented as a citation.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source which is published and does not give credit to the author.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author or that source of information.¹**
- Copying and pasting information from the web and not cite the source is not a plagiarism because many information in the web does not have an author.

2. When you quote, you can make changes in some circumstances.

¹ Euclid University. *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period One*. (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 8-10.

- Added words. You should use brackets to add words in a citation.**²
- Foreign language. You should remove accents and other marks.
- Citation in original. If you quote material that contains a citation to another work, you must precise it.
- Added emphasis. When you want to add emphasis, use parenthesis.
3. **The best order to follow when you begin with a paper is to move from:**
- The hypothesis to a question and the to the topic.
- The question to the topic and then to the hypothesis.
- The topic to the hypothesis and then to the question.
- The topic to the question and then to the hypothesis.**³
4. **When you are revising your paper, you have to write your final introduction and conclusion. What is the thing that should appear both in introduction and conclusion?**
- The context.
- The claim.**⁴
- The question of the study.
- The significance of the question.

² EUCLID, 70.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. Rev. by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 18-20.

⁴ Turabian, 70-73.

5. How to cite using the in-text citation? Choose the right reference

- Morey, Peter, and Amina Yaqin. 2011. *Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.⁵
- Peter, Morey, and Yaqin Amina. 2011. Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Morey, Peter, and Amina Yaqin. 2011. Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Morey, Peter, and Amina Yaqin. 2011. Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. 50-55.

6. How to cite using the bibliography citation style? Choose the correct answer.

- Morey, Peter and Yaqin Amina. Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2011), 52.
- Peter, Morey and Amina Yaqin. Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2011), 52.
- Peter, Morey and Amina Yaqin, *Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2011.⁶
- Peter Morey and Amina Yaqin, Framing Muslims: Stereotyping and Representation after 9/11. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2011, 52.

⁵ Turabian, 129.

⁶ Turabian, 91.

7. **One of these sentences reflect the paradigm which is concerned with quantitative research**

- Pragmatic researchers propose than within the same study, methods can be combined in creative ways to more fully or completely understand a research problem.
- Postpositivism refers to the thinking that developed from logical positivism, a school of thought that maintains that all knowledge can be derived from direct observation and logical inferences based on that observations.⁷**
- The basic tenet of constructivism is that reality is not socially, culturally, and historically constructed.
- The critical theory paradigm includes feminist perspectives, racialized discourses, queer theory, and disability inquiry.

8. **The chapter three of a qualitative research is made by:**

- The identification of other relevant research so that you can situate your work in the literature, as well as draw from the literature to inform your study.
- Description of the findings.
- Description of meanings tied to each finding.
- The research sample, overview of information needed, research design, methods of data collection, analysis and synthesis, ethical consideration, issues of trustworthiness and limitation of the study.⁸**

9. **Regarding general rules for abbreviations in ‘WHO Style Guide’**

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from the Beginning to the End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 7-8.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 68-78.

- The number of abbreviations may be as much as you need.
- A separate list of abbreviation is needed, even if the text has only few abbreviations.
- All abbreviations should be defined and spelt out the first time they are used, unless likely to be familiar to readers.⁹**
- You should put the full stop at the end of the sentence, even if the abbreviation end with a full stop.

10. **The general rules for headings are:**

- Numbered headings are not obligatory in WHO Technique Report Series.
- When it is possible, limit the number of heading to three.¹⁰**
- You should use or not use initial capital letter for the first word.
- There is a full point for headings of chapter titles.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from the Beginning to the End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publication, 2008.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack for Period One (1)*. Wachinton DC: Euclid University press, 2015.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Researchs Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 8th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb and Joseph M. Williams. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

⁹ World Health Organization, WHO style guide (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 3-4.

¹⁰ World Health Organization, 12.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.